

1 **Control of Xist by MRE11 indicates Xist activation in tumorigenesis is associated with double-strand break**
2 **DNA repair.**

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7 We recently described control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation in
8 humans, Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and Rb1, showed activation of Xist in breast
9 cancer and in lung cancer in humans, and subsequently described control of Xist multiple nuclear effectors
10 important for repair of DNA at double-strand breaks, including the p53-associated molecule 53bp1, the breast
11 cancer susceptibility gene BRCA1, and 53bp1-associated molecule Rif1. 53bp1, BRCA1 and Rif1 participate
12 in repair of the DNA at double-strand breaks, suggesting that functions of the MRN (MRE11/Rad50/Nbs1)
13 complex (1) may be important for or during Xist activation prior to and/or during solid tissue transformation in
14 humans. We demonstrate here control of Xist by the MRN complex component MRE11. Pathways important
15 for repair of DNA double-strand breaks, and thus DNA damage repair machinery and signaling molecules
16 activated by DNA damage are biologically relevant to the molecular mechanisms underlying Xist activation
17 during transformation in humans.

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